

Imaging of DNA Molecules by Atomic Force Microscope

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Abstract - This paper explores suitable conditions for the imaging of DNA molecules by atomic force microscope (AFM). As a typical biological macro-molecule, DNA with genetic information has attracted extensive attention, which is an important research subject in biomedicine. In this work, 3-Aminopropyl Triethyl Silane (APTES), Ni^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were used to modify the surface of mica substrate, and DNA molecules were adhered to the mica surface through the physical interaction of charges. The DNA molecules were imaged using an AFM under both air conditions and liquid conditions. By analyzing the images of DNA molecules obtained in the experiments, it was found that the mica surface modified with Ni^{2+} had the best imaging quality under the liquid condition. This work will be useful for the study of high quality AFM imaging of DNA molecules, and the manipulation of DNA molecules by AFM mechanical forces.

Keywords—Atomic force microscope (AFM); DNA molecule; APTES; Ni^{2+} ; Mg^{2+}

I. INTRODUCTION

In 1986, Binnig et al invented the atomic force microscope (AFM) after the invention of scanning tunneling microscope (STM) [1]. It is a milestone in nanotechnology that scientists are able to observe the nano-world in both air and liquid. As a member of scanning probe microscope (SPM) family, AFM can be used to detect surface structures of conductive and nonconductive materials with atomic resolution. It can also be used for the study of many physical properties such as adhesion [2,3], friction [4] and elasticity [5,6]. Thus, AFM has its unique advantages with a wide range of applications, compared to optical microscopes and STMs [7-10].

In recent years, AFM has been used for the study of biomolecules^[11] and DNA molecules [12-16]. Ido used the NiCl_2 solution to modify the mica surface and measured the supercoil pitch of DNA molecules [17]. Pyne scanned the secondary structure of DNA molecules using the same modification method [18]. Rief et al studied the force curves of double-stranded DNA molecules by AFM single-molecule force spectroscopy and the molecules were unwound as single-stranded DNAs with the external force [19]. Jun et al

used APTES to modify the mica substrate and manipulate DNA molecules. Wu et al used Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} to modify mica substrates and study the impact of ion concentration on the network of DNA molecules [20].

In this paper, APTES, Ni^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were used to modify fluorphlogopite mica surfaces, and DNA molecules were adhered to the mica surfaces for AFM imaging. The DNA molecules were imaged using an AFM under both air conditions and liquid conditions. Finally, the effects of different ionic liquids on the AFM imaging of DNA molecules were analyzed and compared under different imaging environments.

II. EXPERIMENT

A. Principle

In a weak alkaline condition, a DNA molecule exhibits a weak electronegativity because the phosphate group of DNA molecule loses H^+ to maintain its static balance. When the mica surface is modified with APTES, it will form a Si-O-Si covalent bond on the surface. Then DNA molecules will be adhered to the mica surface due to the effect of electrostatic interaction, produced by the amino portion of APTES. When the mica surface is modified with Ni^{2+} , positive divalent metal ions will be adhered on the surface of the substrate, and form an ion bridge together with the phosphate groups of DNA molecules. The Ni^{2+} can not only bond to the phosphate backbone but also bond to the bases of DNA molecules. Compared to APTES and Ni^{2+} , Mg^{2+} can only bond to the phosphate backbone.

B. Materials and Equipment

The fluorphlogopite mica was purchased from Taiyuan Fluorphlogopite Mica Company, Changchun, China. Lambda DNA molecules (48, 502 bp, 500 ng/ μL) were the products of Life Technology, and purchased from Jilin YiXiang Technology Company, Changchun, China. APTES, Solid Nickel Chloride and Magnesium Chloride were all purchased from Jintaihua Glass Company, Changchun, China. Deionized water, was purified by the Milli-Q system, and the resistance coefficient was higher than 18M Ω ·cm.

The AFM used in the experiments was the NanoWizard Life Science-JPK (Germany), which was set on an antivibration table and electromagnetically shielded to minimize external perturbations during data recording. The Bruker probe, DNP-10 (silicon nitride probe, tip radius of curvature 10 nm.), which was bought from the company of BoRui Instruments Shanghai.

C. Experiment

The TE buffer (100mM NaCl, 10mM Tris-HCl, 1mM EDTA, PH = 8.0) was used to dilute DNA molecules. In the experiments, the concentration of DNA solution was 20 ng/ μ L, which was the mixture of 2 μ L DNA solution and 48 μ L TE buffer solution, and it was kept in a refrigerator at the temperature of 4°C. The concentration of APTES aqueous solution was 1% (volume ratio 1:100). The solution was diluted with 10 μ L APTES and 1 mL re-distilled water (deionized water through two distillations). 0.1188g $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals and 0.0023g $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ crystals were put into two different centrifuge tubes, and then added some deionized water to make the total volume to 50mL, and vibrated 30s. Thus, 10mM NiCl_2 solution and 10 mM MgCl_2 solution were obtained.

D. Sample preparation

(1) Pretreatment of mica: Stripped the mica several times with white transparent tapes, until a complete layer was obtained. Then rinsed the fresh mica tablets 3 times with re-distilled water, and dried in the air.

(2) Modification of mica tablets: 2 μ L APTES solution, NiCl_2 solution and MgCl_2 solution were put into three different sealing films. Put the air-dried mica into the sealing film with the tweezers, to ensure that the solutions were spread over the entire surface of the mica sheet. 2 min later, removed the mica tablets with the tweezers, and dried in the air.

(3) Adsorption of DNA molecules: 1 μ L DNA solution was slowly dropped onto the modified mica surface, and spread out with the clean sealing film. The droplet was spread on the mica surface with the molecular combing method.

(4) Mica cleaning: Removed the sealing film after waiting for 3~5 min in (3), cleaned the mica a few times with the deionized water, and dried in the air.

(5) DNA molecular imaging: Put the sample onto the JPK AFM system scanning platform, adjusted parameters and prepared for imaging.

E. AFM imaging

DNA samples were placed on the ion-modified mica surface in the JPK AFM system scanning platform. The AFM system parameters are IGain=20.0 Hz, PGain=0.0010, set-point=300mV, and scanning speed=1.00Hz. The imaging mode was contact mode, and the image size was 512×512 pixels. All the images were processed using the JPK Data Processing Software. The height and width of DNA molecules were also measured.

A. APTES modification

Figs. 1(a) and 1(b) show the images of λ DNA molecules on the mica surfaces. The molecules were immobilized with APTES in the air and liquid. The DNA molecules exhibit a good linearity with high resolution and are closely attached to the mica surface.

It can be seen from Figs. 1(a) and 1(b) that the flatness of the APTES modified mica surface is not good under liquid conditions. Thus, other methods should be investigated and developed to improve it.

Fig. 1 AFM images of DNA molecules with APTES modified mica surfaces. (a) In the air; (b) In the liquid.

Comparing Fig. 1(a) and Fig. 1(b), it can be found that the adhesion force between the DNA molecules and mica surface in the air is significantly larger than that in the liquid. From Fig. 1(b), it can be seen that the DNA molecules are clearly higher in the liquid and the adhesion force between the DNA molecules and mica surface is not strong so that it is easier to manipulate the DNA molecules by mechanical force.

B. Ni^{2+} and Mg^{2+} modifications

Figs. 2(a) and 2(b) show the images of λ DNA molecules on the mica surfaces. The molecules were immobilized with Ni^{2+} in the air and liquid. The DNA molecules exhibit a good linearity. Comparing Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 2(b), it can be clearly observed that the DNA molecules in the liquid are wider and thicker than those in the air. After the analysis of the height distributions of DNA molecules, it can be seen that their heights in the air are generally lower than those in the liquid.

Fig. 2 AFM images of DNA molecules with Ni^{2+} modified mica surfaces. (a) In the air; (b) In the liquid.

Fig. 3 is the image of DNA molecules on the Mg^{2+} modified mica surface in the air. From Fig. 3, it can be found that the DNA molecules show certain linearity. The samples were also imaged in the liquid, but it was difficult to find them on the Mg^{2+} modified mica surface. In this case, Mg^{2+} might be not suitable for the application.

Fig. 3 AFM image of DNA molecules with the Mg^{2+} modified mica surface in the air.

By analyzing the imaging results of three types of modified mica surfaces, conclusions can be made that DNA molecules can be immobilized well when the mica surfaces were modified with Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and APTES in air conditions. However, in liquid conditions, only the Ni^{2+} and APTES modified mica surfaces can be used for the imaging of DNA molecules, while the Mg^{2+} cannot be used for the imaging of DNA molecules in the experiments.

Based on the measurements of several groups of DNA molecules, the height and width distributions of the molecules under various ionic modification conditions in air and liquid conditions are obtained, as shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1 Sizes of DNA molecules in different modification solutions under air conditions

Solution	Height (nm)	Width (nm)
APTES	0.74 ± 0.26	10.37 ± 2.54
Ni^{2+}	0.84 ± 0.37	27.83 ± 8.12
Mg^{2+}	0.87 ± 0.31	24.55 ± 2.76

Table 2 Sizes of DNA molecules in different modification solutions under liquid conditions

Solution	Height (nm)	Width (nm)
APTES	1.20 ± 0.38	32.68 ± 4.53
Ni^{2+}	1.61 ± 0.30	39.03 ± 10.21

Comparing the data from the two tables, it can be seen that the height of the DNA molecules in the liquid is significantly higher than that in the air, and the width is clearly wider. The results are closer to the theoretical value in liquid conditions. This might be due to the fact that the forces

between the needle tip and the DNA molecule in the liquid were smaller than those in the air. Thus, liquid conditions are more suitable for the imaging of DNA molecules than the air conditions.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, three types of solutions were used to modify the mica surfaces, then the differences between the imaging of DNA molecules in air and liquid conditions were analyzed by AFM. It was found that DNA images could not be obtained in liquid conditions when the mica surface was modified with Mg^{2+} . When the mica surface was modified with Ni^{2+} and APTES, DNA molecules were easily imaged in both air and liquid conditions. In addition, DNA molecules were more closely adhered to the mica surface when the mica surface was modified with APTES. As for Ni^{2+} , DNA molecules were adsorbed slightly on the mica surface, and their sizes were close to their theoretical value, which was more suitable for studying their detailed information. Normally, DNA molecules are always in the physiological environment, thus, using Ni^{2+} to modify the mica surfaces and adsorb DNA molecules in liquid conditions is a good choice for the imaging of DNA molecules. This conclusion will be useful for the study of high quality AFM imaging of DNA molecules, and the manipulation of DNA molecules by AFM mechanical forces.

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